

Collaborative, multidisciplinary, international, and societal relevant: A framework combining challenge-based learning and thesis writing across European universities

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ABSTRACT

ECIU University is an EU-funded European University initiated by a network consisting of 13 universities across Europe. At its core is collaborative learning and research on a European level in close connection with various stakeholders to tackle societal challenges. Learners are engaged in joint project work based on the approach of challenge-based learning (CBL). Here, learners are actively involved in a real and relevant setting. Teams are composed of learners coming from different cultural backgrounds, disciplines, and levels of progress in their individual studies. A challenge within the ECIU framework starts with a “Big Idea” in the area of the UN Sustainable Development Goal 11 “Sustainable cities and communities” that has potential for societal impact. ECIU University offers four types of challenges that differ in length and depth. Within this paper, the first run of an ECIU Strategic

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Challenge, the most complex challenge type, is introduced. The Strategic Challenge is a six-month format that combines individual working phases while writing on one's master's thesis with collaborative working phases while cooperating closely in the team challenge. Hence, it offers a framework in which the progress of challenge and master's theses are expected to go hand in hand. The concept of how students collaborate in the Strategic Challenge builds up upon the Erasmus+ projects COLIBRI (Collaboration and Innovation for better, personalized, and IT-supported Teaching) and its follow up EPIC (Improving Employability through Internationalisation and Collaboration).

1 INTRODUCTION

The ECIU² University is an Erasmus+ funded alliance that brings together 13 European universities³ and one associated member to address societal challenges faced by European countries. Students and university teachers from all ECIU partners, stakeholders from business and public organizations, as well as citizens come together to engage, investigate and act to find innovative solutions for real life challenges with real societal impact. The educational framework of the ECIU University offers a creative, inspiring, and meaningful learning environment in engineering education. It is based on the pedagogical approach of challenge-based learning (CBL). Within the framework, four types of challenges are offered: Nano Challenges, Mini Challenges, Standard Challenges, and Strategic Challenges [1]. The challenge types differ in their length resp. workload (30 hours to 360 hours) and depth (level of CBL phases). This paper introduces the first run of an ECIU Strategic Challenge. The pilot of the Strategic Challenge is a six-month format that combines participating in a challenge with the writing of individual master's thesis. The format has started in February 2022.

2 FRAMEWORK

2.1 Challenge-based learning in the ECIU context

Challenge-based learning provides an efficient and effective educational framework for learning to solve real-life challenges. The framework aims at the acquisition of disciplinary knowledge while developing transferable skills. Learners are engaged in team projects while being actively involved in a real and relevant setting [2]. The teams are composed of learners coming from different cultural backgrounds, disciplines, and levels of progress in their studies. With different stakeholders involved, CBL aims to find collaboratively developed solutions that are

² ECIU is the European Consortium of Innovative Universities.

³ University of Twente, Aalborg University, Dublin University, Hamburg University of Technology, Kaunas University of Technology, Linköping University, Tampere University, University of Barcelona, University of Aveiro, University of Stavanger, University of Trento, Institut National des Sciences Appliquées, Lodz University, and TEC de Monterrey as associated institution.

environmentally, socially and economically sustainable [3]. Hence, the learning experience is international and intercultural, multidisciplinary, and collaborative. Within the learners-driven approach, students are enabled to take complete ownership of their self-defined challenge, cooperating closely with the teachers and (external) partners in a co-learning environment.

A challenge within the ECIU framework starts with a “Big Idea” in the area of the UN Sustainable Development Goal 11 “Sustainable cities and communities” that has potential for societal impact. The approach is made up of three phases: Engage, Investigate, and Act (Fig. 1). Constant documentation, reflection, and sharing is an elementary part of the entire process [1].

Fig. 1. CBL circle [4]

The engage phase is initiated by sharing the Big Idea, which is usually provided by (external) partners. Based on the Big Idea, the learners themselves define essential questions tackling related aspects according to their interest, or which skills and competencies they want to further develop. This leads to the creation of their individual actionable challenge, which is at the same time the result of the first phase. In the second phase of the CBL cycle, the learners formulate the basis of sustainable solutions to their individual challenges by conducting the actual research and analysis according to their skills and expertise. The investigate phase results in learning outcomes like reports and presentations demonstrating individual conclusions. Within the act phase, the learners implement and evaluate their solutions ideally with an authentic audience highlighting their societal impact [1].

The teacher in the overall framework guides the learners during the whole process. While promoting team culture, being challenging to the participants, and supporting learners to create actual impact, the teacher takes the role of a facilitator.

2.2 Idea of the concept

Combining the approach of challenge-based learning and writing a master's thesis shapes a novel and innovative pedagogical format. It combines working on a challenge in an international, multidisciplinary team with individual working phases when writing one's master's thesis according to home university guidelines. The concept of how students collaborate in the Strategic Challenge is based on the former Erasmus+ projects COLIBRI (Collaboration and Innovation for better, personalized, and IT-supported Teaching) and its follow up EPIC (Improving Employability through Internationalisation and Collaboration). EPIC aims to increase employability through closer collaboration between students, academia, and industry. It provides a framework for international student projects in close collaboration with companies [5]. The joint student projects in the EPIC framework deal with similar issues: different start and end times at participating institutions, different requirements from different institutions, assessment and documentation varies between institutions. To face these aspects, different models of collaboration were developed within the EPIC project that combine joint work and thesis writing [6]. These models serve as a basis for developing the Strategic Challenge collaboration framework.

3 PROJECT DESCRIPTION

3.1 Strategic Challenge as a unique master's thesis opportunity

The Strategic Challenge offers an exceptional opportunity for advanced master students to collaboratively work on a societal challenge in an international and multidisciplinary team while also individually writing a master's thesis that is linked to the topic of the challenge. Within the framework, the progress of challenge and master's theses are expected to go hand in hand and ensuring to benefit from one another.

As all ECIU challenges, the Strategic Challenge starts with a "Big Idea" in the area of the UN Sustainable Development Goal 11 "Sustainable cities and communities" and has potential for societal impact. The Big Idea in the case at hand is to develop a climate neutral campus in Europe with innovative ideas and bold solutions and thereby, advance climate protection and reduce CO₂ emission. Students are asked to develop concepts that enable their home university or any other university to reach a climate neutral campus in the future.

In the first realization of the described concept, each ECIU partner institution is asked to find one academic advisor and one master student to participate in the challenge. Participants are selected with respect to their readiness to begin their thesis and with respect to multidisciplinary. For the first run of the ECIU Strategic Challenge nine eligible students from seven ECIU institutions have been selected. Before the challenge officially starts the academic advisors are invited to a Supervisors Kick Off to learn more about the main challenge. As a result they are asked to inform their respective master student in order to get prepared for the challenge start: this means, to collect first ideas on a climate neutral campus in

Europe, however, not to elaborate on a concrete master's thesis topic yet. The actual topics are expected to be developed alongside the actionable ECIU challenge so that the master students are still flexible.

3.2 Phases and milestones of the Strategic Challenge

According to ECIU University's challenge-based learning framework, the Strategic Challenge includes three phases:

1. Phase of engagement: Students from ECIU partners enter the challenge team, narrow down the topic, develop essential questions, and define their actionable challenge.
2. Phase of investigation: With different stakeholders involved, students research and engage in activities to define a solution to the challenge. While collaboratively working in the challenge team students also work towards their respective master's thesis that are content wise linked to the challenge.
3. Phase of action: Solutions are prepared and master's theses are written. The challenge team opens the findings to society. This includes either the implementation of the outcome or delivering a product.

Fig. 2 illustrates the framework of the Strategic Challenge and shows how the three phases of CBL are combined with individual thesis writing.

Fig. 2. Strategic Challenge framework [7]

The Strategic Challenge officially starts with a Kick Off event for the students. The online Kick Off marks the beginning of the engagement phase. Apart from getting to know one another and learning about the steps of CBL the Kick Off primarily aims at finding subgroups to form teams according to the students' interests and ideas for their master's theses. This is to facilitate that the student teams can develop an actionable challenge that can be linked to their individual theses respectively.

In the first ECIU Strategic Challenge, nine students from seven ECIU institutions work in three teams of three students each on in total three self-developed

challenges based on the Big Idea of "Climate neutral Campus in Europe" (Fig. 3). The academic advisors are invited to join the sessions of the Kick Off to provide feedback to ideas. Also, they participate in a discussion on the supervisor's role in the overall Strategic Challenge.

Fig. 3. Strategic Challenge 2022 [8]

The Strategic Challenge is structured by four milestone meetings for the whole group of students (one as a face-to-face meeting). Those allow the student teams to work self-determined on their individual challenge. However, during the engage phase weekly support is offered to the subteams to ensure that all teams get on the right path and manage to develop their actionable challenge. In the phases of investigation and action, biweekly support is offered to the teams to reflect e.g. on their team progress, stakeholder management, struggles, and final outcome. Also, various workshops related to team work and project work are offered throughout the challenge to promote skills and competences required to successfully complete the project.

Continual reflection and documentation accompany all three phases. The students are asked to keep a team learning diary and submit a team reflection report at the end of the challenge. Also, opportunities to share (interim) results with the wider community are created.

3.3 Challenges of the design

The first run of the Strategic Challenge faced a few challenges that were at least attributed to the internationality of the participants. Due to different timelines and regulations of their home universities (different start points, different total duration, different submission dates) the students turned out to be less flexible concerning their thesis writing than expected. Hence, some students had already defined their thesis topic when entering the engagement phase as illustrated by figure 4. This challenges the approach of CBL that typically allows learners to individually move

from a “Big Idea” to a concrete and actionable challenge. Hence, the engagement phase in the Strategic Challenge was limited since also the already approved topics had to be taken into consideration when developing a concrete challenge.

Fig. 4. Illustration of different timelines [9]

Different submission dates might have also affected the work process. While some students had to submit their thesis before the end of the challenge, others still have weeks beyond the closing event to finish their thesis. This might have had an impact on the groups' progress and outcome.

In the learner-centered approach of challenge-based learning, the teacher usually acts as a facilitator. In the Strategic Challenge, the constellation is more complex as each student is additionally supervised in his or her master's thesis by a local academic advisor. The supervisor's role is primarily to supervise the thesis. Therefore, active communication and a clear allocation of roles are essential to enable a productive learning environment and to avoid potential conflicts.

4 CONCLUSION

The first run of the Strategic Challenge has been promising so far. The students worked in three subgroups on a challenge they had developed themselves from the Big Idea of "Climate neutral Campus in Europe". Although the engagement phase had to be adapted to the circumstances (some prior to the start of the Strategic Challenge approved master's theses topics) the students went through all further steps of CBL to the (planned) implementation or (initial) development of a product/prototype. The students' commitment and the contribution they made to the project were great. Moreover, they further developed future skills like international team communication, project management, and co-operation with stakeholders. The exchange of ideas and experiences on a European level seemed to be inspiring for everyone involved. Hence, the first Strategic Challenge offered students not only a novel opportunity for writing a master's thesis but also a unique learning experience. The main working phase is finished by now, however, the evaluation of the project is still running. First verbal feedback that we received in several settings was in general positive but also drew attention to challenging aspects of the format. Overall, the feedback indicates that the format of the ECIU Strategic Challenge is perceived as rewarding by the majority of the participants. Apart from a final online evaluation that

is now in progress to find out how students and academic advisors value their participation, the group reflection reports will be evaluated to critically reflect on the concept and to derive potential improvements. In addition, interviews will be conducted with some of the participants to get a deeper understanding of what experiences they have made.

Based on these results, the concept of the Strategic Challenge will be optimized. The improvements will be implemented in future ECIU Strategic Challenges.

REFERENCES

- [1] Nichols, M., Cator, K., Torres, M., Henderson, D. (2016), Challenge-Based Learner User Guide. Redwood City, CA: Digital Promise.
<https://cbl.digitalpromise.org/2016/08/30/challenge-based-learning-guide/> (29.06.2022)
- [2] Tecnológico de Monterrey (2015), Challenge-Based Learning. *Edu Trends* Year 2, number 5, October 2015. <https://observatory.tec.mx/edutrends-challengebased-learning> (29.06.2022)
- [3] Kohn Rådberg, K., Lundqvist, U., Malmqvist, J., Hagvall Svensson, O. (2020), From CDIO to challenge-based learning experiences – expanding student learning as well as societal impact? *European Journal of Engineering Education* Vol. 45, No.1, pp. 22–37. 2022)
- [4] Center for Teaching and Learning, Hamburg University of Technology (2022): CBL Circle.
- [5] EPIC, <http://epic.agu.edu.tr/> (29.06.2022)
- [6] Pedersen, J. M., Jensen, J. V. (2018), International Student Projects – How to make it happen. *ETALEE 2018, Exploring Teaching for Active Learning in Engineering Education*. IngeniørUddannelsernes Pædagogiske Netværk, IUPN, pp. 17-26.
- [7] Center for Teaching and Learning, Hamburg University of Technology (2022): Strategic Challenge Framework.
- [8] Center for Teaching and Learning, Hamburg University of Technology (2022): Strategic Challenge 2022.
- [9] Center for for Teaching and Learning, Hamburg University of Technology (2022): Illustration of different timelines.